

MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING MODEL FOR SELECTING SUPPLIERS' OFFERS**Mukhanbetkaliyev D.,***22a Satpaev str., 050013, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Serbin V.***PhD, Associate Professor of Kazakh National Research Technical**University named after K.I. Satpayev,**22a Satpaev str., 050013, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) is one of the main decision-making problems which aims to determine the best alternative by considering more than one criterion in the selection process. MCDM has manifold tools and methods that can be applied in different fields from finance to engineering design. This scientific article presented a multi-criteria decision-making model for selecting supplier proposals. The developed model is based on the analysis of several criteria that may influence the choice of supplier. The criteria were classified based on their impact on the organization's business processes. The study showed that the model allows accurate and reliable decisions in this area.

Keywords: multi-criteria, decision-making, model, selecting, supplier, business, processes.

In today's environment, different companies are faced with the problem of effectively choosing from many different supplier offers. The supplier selection process is an important task for many organizations. Decisions made in this area can significantly impact the success and profitability of a business. At the same time, choosing suppliers is often complicated due to the many options available and the variety of criteria that need to be taken into account. In such a situation, the use of multi-criteria decision-making models can be a very useful tool. The choice is not always obvious, since price and quality are not the only criteria. It is relevant to develop an information system that allows making an effective optimal decision based on a multi-criteria model.

The decision-making process is essential in addressing any decision, as it is a complex mental process aimed at finding a desirable result while considering various aspects.[1] This process can be rational or irrational, utilizing implicit or explicit assumptions influenced by factors such as physiological, biological, cultural, and social elements, as well as authority and risk levels. The complexity of decision-making can be affected by these aspects [2].

Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) or Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA), is one of the most accurate methods of decision-making, and it can be known as a revolution in this field [3].

MCDM involves considering both qualitative and quantitative criteria to identify the best solution, with criteria such as cost, price, and quality being common in decision-making. Expert groups assign different weights to criteria based on their importance in a specific case. MCDM is applicable to everyday problems but becomes crucial in more significant matters such as capital levels, where proper structuring and explicit evaluation of criteria are necessary [4,5].

Various types of MCDM methods have been developed by different authors over the last few decades, differing in algorithm complexity, weighting methods, representation of preferences evaluation criteria, handling uncertain data, and data aggregation. MCDM has

diverse applications in economics, finance, engineering design, as highlighted in a comprehensive reviews by Aruldoss M. [1], Velasquez M. [2], Taherdoost H.[3], Shamsavarani A.M. [4], Pramanik [5], Habenicht W.[6] et al.

Further research was conducted on real data collected from various organizations. The results showed that the developed model provides fairly accurate and reliable results when making decisions regarding the selection of suppliers. Moreover, the model can be easily modified and adapted to different situations and requirements.

1 Research and development methodology

The following methods were used as research methods: mathematical modeling, method of paired comparisons, testing, experiment.

BPMN notation was used to describe the business process for selecting a supplier. [4] BPM notation allows you to visualize business processes using graphical diagrams such as Flowcharts or BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation). This makes processes more visual and understandable for all participants, including business analysts, managers and performers [5].

2 Statement of the problem

Let K be a supercriterion including kn criteria, where $n \in [1;4]$. kn includes $i \rightarrow$ indicators, where $i \in [1;m]$, $m \rightarrow \infty$.

For example, $k_1 \diamond$ product quality consists of indicators:

1) Size 2) Color 3) Functionality 4) Power 5) Expiration date and more.

Each kn criterion has its own weight V_n , $V \in [1;10]$,

It is required to develop a multi-criteria decision-making model based on a set of criteria k_1 depending on V .

A generalized decision-making model for selecting supplier proposals is presented in accordance with Figure 1.

Pic.1. Generalized decision-making model for choosing supplier proposals

The importance of each criterion was determined using the paired comparison method. The weight for each criterion was experimentally determined: $V_1=0.4$; $V_2=0.3$; $V_3=0.2$; $V_4=0.1$.

Thus, the model, taking into account the weight of each criterion, will take the form(1):

$$S_n = k_{n1} * V_1 + k_{n2} * V_2 + k_{n3} * V_3 + k_{n4} * V_4, \quad (1)$$

$n=1..5.$

This formula (1) is applicable only for four criteria (Table 1)

Table 1

Supplier Offer Comparison Matrix

Supplier organization			Name 1	Name 2	Name 3	Name 4	Name 5
№	Name of criterion	Weight,%	85000				
1	K1 - Compliance with product and service requirements, %	V1	K ₁₁	K ₁₂	K ₁₃	K ₁₄	K ₁₅
2	K2 - Service product cost	V2	K ₂₁	K ₂₂	K ₂₃	K ₂₄	K ₂₅
3	K3 - Supplier experience, %	V3	K ₃₁	K ₃₂	K ₃₃	K ₃₄	K ₃₅
4	K4 - Implementation period, days	V4	K ₄₁	K ₄₂	K ₄₃	K ₄₄	K ₄₅
TOTAL, %:			S1	S2	S3	S4	S5

The next step was to evaluate the suppliers' proposals based on the specified criteria. For all criteria 1 and 3, a scale from 0% to 100% was used. For criteria 2 and 4, for example, the lowest cost method was used to convert costs to percentages. 100% matched the lowest price. A percentage of the cost was calculated relative to other prices. A similar method was used to convert delivery time to a single percentage measurement scale.

All scores for each criterion were multiplied by its weight and the results were summed up in K for each supplier proposal. This produced a final score for each sentence. Next, the final scores for each supplier proposal were compared and the proposal with the highest score was selected in accordance with the specified criteria and weights.

If each criterion has N_{ij} indicators, then the formula will be transformed into (2):

$$K = (k_{1,1} * V_{1,1} + k_{1,2} * V_{1,2} + k_{1,3} * V_{1,3} + k_{1,4} * V_{1,4}) * V_1 + (k_{2,1} * V_{2,1} + k_{2,2} * V_{2,2} + k_{2,3} * V_{2,3} + k_{2,4} * V_{2,4}) * V_2 + (k_{3,1} * V_{3,1} + k_{3,2} * V_{3,2} + k_{3,3} * V_{3,3} + k_{3,4} * V_{3,4}) * V_3 + (k_{4,1} * V_{4,1} + k_{4,2} * V_{4,2} + k_{4,3} * V_{4,3} + k_{4,4} * V_{4,4}) * V_4 \quad (2)$$

Consectary

Objectivity: the model allows you to take into account not only one criterion, but also many different factors, which makes the selection process more objective and reasonable.

Flexibility: the model allows you to adjust the weights of criteria in accordance with the needs and preferences of the organization, as well as take into account changes in market conditions and consumer requirements.

Transparency: The model makes it possible to clearly present and explain decisions made based on the assessment of each criterion and its weight.

Conclusion

This scientific article presented a multi-criteria decision-making model for selecting supplier proposals. The developed model is based on the analysis of several criteria that may influence the choice of supplier. The study showed that the model allows accurate and reliable decisions in this area.

Further research can be carried out to optimize and improve the developed model, as well as compare it with other existing multi-criteria analysis models. It is also worth paying attention to the application of the model in various industries and situations to evaluate its versatility and effectiveness.

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